

OpenWebSearch.EU

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

Deliverable D6.1: ELSA-Catalogue & Code of Conduct for Open Web Search

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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Project Coordinator	Prof. Dr. Michael Granitzer, University of Passau

ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
IT4I@VSB	Technical University of Ostrava
CERN	Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
CSC	Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy (IT Center for Science)
NLNET	Stichting NLnet
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
SUMA-EV	SuMa e.V. - Verein für freien Wissenszugang (Associated Partner)

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document describes the deliverable D6.1: “ELSA-Catalogue & Code of Conduct for open Web search” of the OpenWebSearch.eu project funded by the EC under the GA 101070014 within the Horizon Europe Framework programme. This first version mainly specifies the methodology and updates in planning as well as first activities conducted in ethical, legal, and societal aspects of the technology created in the project. The next versions will focus on the content of the Catalogue and Code of Conduct which will be created according to the methodology and plans of this deliverable.

v. Document Management

History of Changes

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Name	Role	Action	Date
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Michael Granitzer (UNI PASSAU)	Coordinator	Review	23 August 2023
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vii. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on initial activities and findings on Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects (ELSA) of open web search and the open web index. These activities consist of the identification of ethical and legal issues and problems, the conduction of workshops and discussions internally and with external experts, and a preliminary summary of the ethical and legal situation. These initial findings will serve as basis for the iterative process that consists of the three phases (a) problem identification, (b) ethics and legal assessment, and (c) design guidelines and codes of conduct. For conducting these phases, all relevant stakeholders are integrated including the task members, the project management, the technology researchers and developers, and external experts. In several workshops with the project members and external ethics and law experts an initial understanding of the ethical and legal aspects could be elaborated. Furthermore, these workshops also initiated the establishment of a community around ELSA. The iterative process will result in the ELSA Catalogue and Code of Conduct in the next, on one side, and final version of this deliverable, on another side. Note that ethical requirements and the management of ethical aspects are also described in the deliverable D9.1, which will be submitted the same time as this deliverable.

1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the initial work on the Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects (ELSA) of the OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS) infrastructure. The creation of this complex and large scale technology needs a lot of efforts, resources, and attention. Besides the technical work, also ethical, legal and societal aspects have to be considered and investigated.

The impact of search engines on people and the society has been broadly investigated. Positive effects and the general importance of search engines are obvious, as they enable people to find information on the Web. However, there are also negative effects of search engines, such as biased search results, user data monitoring and profile building, or the reinforcement of societal stereotypes and power structures. Hence, search engines raise a lot of ethical questions that need to be addressed.

In addition to ethical questions, the operation of a search engine also raises legal questions. For example, the content that is gathered, processed, and shared by the search engine requires close attention. Illegal content, copyrighted content, or content with personal information is subject to legal regulations. Furthermore, the liability of the search engine operation needs to be clarified. Thus, a careful analysis is needed to understand the legal situation and context of search engines and to comply with current law.

This deliverable is the first of a series of three deliverables on ELSA (M12, M24, M36). It is important to mention that this document provides initial work that will be gradually updated, improved, and extended in the next two years. The final version will be published on the project website as a guideline how to take care on ethics when creating search engine technology.

The next section describes some general methodological concepts that have been used for the initial elaboration of the ethical, legal and societal aspects. Section 3 describes the ethical dimension of search engine in more detail. Section 4 provides an overview of the legal situation at the current stage in the project. Section 5 names some societal considerations and aspects. Finally, an outlook of the future work is provided in the last section.

2. Methodology and Activities

This section describes general methodological approaches and initial activities that have been performed to elaborate ethical, legal, and societal aspects.

2.1 General methodology

In order to initiate the elaboration of ethical, legal, and societal aspects, an initial methodology is applied that consists of four key activities:

- a) the elaboration of a conceptual explanation of open web search technology,
- b) the elaboration of issues and problems,
- c) the discussion of these issues and potential solutions with external experts, and
- d) preliminary summaries and frameworks of the outcomes.

These activities are applied particularly on the elaboration of ethical and legal aspects, and to some extent, to the societal aspects. The preliminary summaries and frameworks will serve as a basis for the upcoming work on ELSA and will be reported in future deliverables. Details of this methodology are

described in the next subsections. The specific methodologies of the ethical, legal, and societal aspects are described in the respective sections below.

The overall strategy to apply ELSA on OWS in the future work consists in an iterative process of three phases (see Figure 1), namely (a) the elaboration and identification of ethical and legal issues, values, and laws, (b) the assessment of concepts, technology, and processes, and (c) the provision of design guidelines and end-user documents. It is planned to conduct two iterations during the project lifetime. This process addresses both the development and the usage of outcomes of OWS. In the first research step (year one) the main focus was put on the elaboration and identification of issues, values, and laws. For the second year, a first round of assessment and design guidelines are planned, and for the third year - a final round.

Figure 1: Overall methodology to apply ELSA on OWS to elaborate the ELSA catalogue and code of conduct.

The outcome of this process will contribute to the planned ELSA Catalogue and Code of Conduct. The ELSA Catalogue will consist of the ethical, legal, and societal issues and requirements, as well as recommendations and guidelines how to mitigate them. The Code of Conduct will consist of various documents that describe how to make use of OWS infrastructure, such as the End User License Agreement (EULA) or the code of ethics.

2.2 Workflow overview diagram

The discussion and elaboration of ELSA needs a good understanding of the technical processes and infrastructure of OWS. Especially people with little technical understanding of the inner structure of search engines need to be provided with an understandable description that explains the key components and processes of the OWS architecture. To this end an illustration has been created including the components and processes together with short descriptions (see Figure 2). The creation of the figure has been performed in collaboration with the technical work packages and the

dissemination work package. This illustration is being used in workshops to explain the OWS architecture. The experiences so far confirmed the usefulness and benefit of this illustration.

Figure 2: Workflow overview illustration. This diagram visualises the technical concept of OpenWebSearch.eu architecture. A better readable version can be found under <https://openwebsearch.eu/the-project/>

2.3 Issue collection

One of the initial steps consisted in the collection of ethical and legal issues, problems, and requirements. This collection was mainly done amongst the consortium members and the working groups of the Open Search Foundation. In order to systematically structure the issues, a table was used with columns of the issue, a description, a related technical component if applicable, and a related ethical value or law. A summary of the collected information is presented in the tables in Sections 3.1 and 4.1.

2.4 Workshops

Workshops have been chosen as the format of discussing ethical, legal, and societal aspects with external experts, as well as with the project members. So far, three workshops of different size and type have been conducted. The results of the workshops are summarised in Section 3.2 and 4.2.

The first was a one-day hybrid workshop conducted on 19-20 April 2023 subsequent to the on-site consortium meeting in Graz, Austria. Seven external persons with ethical expertise and seven with legal expertise participated besides 20 project members. The workshop was structured with an inspirational talk of two ethical experts, a group discussion on ethical and legal issues, and finally, a plenary

discussion on the results of the group discussions. The discussion groups were carefully assembled, so that each group consisted of project members with and without technical expertise, as well as either ethical or legal experts. Thus, the external experts were informed about the OWS technology and the project members got access to ethical or legal expertise. The results are described in the next sections.

The overall workshop design was guided by the design studio Invisible Lab¹ that is specialised in defining methodologies for requirements analysis of the design of artifacts. Haptic elements symbolising issues and solutions have been created that were placed on a three-dimensional physical board. The dimensions included urgency, feasibility, and action timeframe. This approach supported the group discussion and helped to focus on the issues and their solutions.

The second workshop was an online mini-workshop that was conducted on 30 June 2023 subsequent to the online consortium meeting. The goal was to make the consortium members one more time aware of ethical problems of search engines. To this end, a collection of examples has been presented that outlined negative ethical impact on users of search engines.

The third workshop was held at the Young Digital Law Conference on 6 July 2023. In a two hours session the concept of OWS was presented to the audience, followed by a group discussion and result presentation. The groups got the task to identify potential legal problems that could be used for an indictment. The audience consisted of conference participants which were PhD students and university staff in the domain of digital law.

The fourth workshop was held as part of an Open Search Foundation Working Group meeting in Berlin on 7-8 August 2023. The main contribution of this workshop to task T6.1 and this deliverable is an extensive elaboration of relevant ethical values in the context of Open Web Search. A summary is presented in Table 2 in Section 3.3.

2.5 Community

In order to involve external people with expertise in ethical or law, a community around these topics is being created.

The initial source of involving external experts was the working groups of the Open Search Foundation (opensearchfoundation.org). A legal and an ethical working group have already been formed a few years ago. In their regular meetings the OWS project members also participate and very often, OWS topics are discussed in this audience as well.

Additionally, in the first ELSA workshop in Graz, 14 external experts in ethics and law have been invited to participate. This way we have got additional stakeholders involved in ELSA. They were not only actively involved in the OWS ELSA discussions, but are also interested in future joint activities.

Dissemination and conference activities is another way to involve external experts in the project activities. As described above (the third workshop), the Young Digital Law Conference in July 2023 was such an attempt. Furthermore, the annual Open Search Symposium (OSSYM) is being used to engage the conference participants in further discussions on ethical and legal topics.

As the project of Next Generation Internet initiative, OWS.eu project conducts so called 3rd party calls (otherwise, Community Programme), which enables the contribution of external experts to particular topics. The first call asked for analysing the legal aspects of the project. Three applications have been

¹ <https://www.invisible-lab.com/>

selected that address legal aspects of the project. This activity will lead to a close collaboration with the beneficiaries of that call.

In general, the community activities are coordinated with Task 6.2 and Work Package 7. Task 6.2 is actively working on fostering the development of an ELSA community as part of its overarching strategy to establish a robust community centered around the Open Web Search theme. Dissemination and Communication activities are coordinated with WP7 tasks for dissemination (T7.1) and communication (T7.3).

3. Ethical Aspects

The overall strategy on elaborating and dealing with ethical aspects follows the approach described in Section 2.1. It is an iterative process of three key phases, namely (a) the elaboration and identification of ethical issues, problems, and values, (b) the ethics assessment of the technology and processes, and (c) the provision of design guidelines and code of conducts. In the first research step (year one) the main focus was put on the elaboration and identification of ethical issues, problems, and values. These results are presented in the section 3. Based on these findings an ethics assessment will be planned and conducted, and consequently, the design guidelines will be elaborated.

3.1 Ethical questions and issues

In several workshops together with the Ethics Working Group of the Open Search Foundation the OWS infrastructure has been analysed using the Workflow Overview Diagram (Figure 2). This initial analysis resulted in a set of ethical questions with respect to the impact on users and society (see Table 1). These questions and issues have been elaborated, to guide the further analysis of the ethical aspects. In particular, the group discussion at the ELSA workshop in Graz was guided by the questions of this table.

ID	Question or Issue
E.01	Danger of crawling problematic content When is content problematic? How can it be decided what to crawl and what to omit? Who decides about what to crawl and what are the criteria? Can the decision be made transparent?
E.02	Access to stored web documents needs clarification Who has access and controls the documents? Who decides where the documents are stored (data centre, country)?
E.03	The content extraction influences the index and search results What exactly is extracted from Web documents? Visible text, hidden comments, all words or are words omitted? Who decides on the algorithm?
E.04	Personal or private information of people can be extracted from content or metadata How should personal information be processed (e.g. deleted, flagged)? Who decides on that? Which data has to be treated with particular care?
E.05	Inconsistent metadata of web documents might influence the search result How should missing metadata in web documents be treated? Which influence could it have on search results? Should it be communicated/flagged?
E.06	Quality of content analysis influences search results

	Can misinterpretation or errors be detected? How are the algorithms developed? What about biases or problematic training data? Who is responsible for quality insurance?
E.07	Decisions on which data is used from metadata or analysed from content analysis Which data should be extracted from metadata? Which data should be calculated through content analysis? Who decides on these decisions?
E.08	The index database structure determines which information is stored (To whom) Is it known (can it be known) which information is stored in the index database? How flexible is the database structure and who can change it?
E.09	Access and ownership of the index data needs clarification Who owns the index? Who has the right to make changes? Who can delete? What are the conditions to use the index?
E.10	Data curation in the index needs clarification How can problematic content be alerted? How should problematic content be treated? Who takes care for problematic content?
E.11	Regulations of downloaded fractions of the index Who owns a downloaded fraction of the index? Who has to manage the downloaded index?
E.12	Usage of the index What are the purposes for which the index is being used? Who benefits from the index? Can all purposes be permitted or are there limits? Who decides on the limits?
E.13	Personal information of end-users How is the users' usage data handled? For what purpose are they used?

Table 1: Ethics (E) questions and issues.

In addition to the initial analysis of ethical problems and issues, a set of examples of ethical problems of existing search engines has been created. These examples were used in the mini-workshop (second workshop) to make the consortium members aware of ethical issues in open web search. Furthermore, it is used as a starting point for the analysis of the ethical aspects. The following ethical issues related to search engines have been discussed.

a) Web search is not only a mirror of a society. It also manifests stereotypes and power structures and it even amplifies distortions and biases.

Prejudices, distortions and misrepresentations in a society are reinforced and amplified. For example, a search for “professional hairstyle women” results in a list of mainly white women, whereas the search for “unprofessional hairstyle women” results in a list of mainly black women. Similarly, a search for the gender-neutral term “doctor” results in a list of mainly male doctors, whereas the search for the term “nurse” results in a list of mainly female nurses. Both examples demonstrate that current stereotypes and prejudices do also appear in search results, which leads to an amplification.

b) Localised/personalised search results: different answers/rankings depending on region, time, device, search history

Search engines take into account temporal and spatial information where and when a search is being made. For example, the search for “turkey” made in Europe in summer typically results in holiday

information in the country Turkey, whereas the same search being made in autumn in the US typically results in the bird as traditional dish at Thanksgiving. While this example demonstrates rather a meaningful personalisation behaviour, there is also an example with a more problematic aspect. An analysis was made on how many pages on human rights relevant issues are retrieved by the search for “Qatar World Cup” in summer 2022. Depending on the country the number of pages with information on human rights issues included in the results list varied a lot (<https://dataethics.eu/what-happens-if-you-google-qatar-world-cup-in-18-different-countries>).

c) Privacy: Tracking + digital surveillance

The data experiment “Made to measure” (Interactive film: madetomeasure.online/en) was presented that demonstrates how a life can be reconstructed based on the stored search queries over a longer time. In this experiment, all Google search queries of several years of a voluntary participant were downloaded and analysed (with consent of the voluntary participant). Then an actress was hired to replay the reconstructed life in front of the original participant, including her job abroad and personal crises. It turned out that the reconstruction was quite accurate.

d) Lack of (algorithmic) transparency and explainability

In general, there is a lack of explainability, transparency and controllability as to how a search result is generated. For example, the search for a support group for a certain disease brings up a pharmaceutical site on this disease. A user might wonder why this happens, but no explanation is being provided. German law requires transparency disclosures about how search (algorithms) work. Users should be enabled to use the content in an informed manner. Information must be easily perceptible, directly accessible and in ‘easy language’. However, a study shows that the information provided by Google is well hidden and difficult to understand (<https://www.die-edienanstalten.de/service/pressemitteilungen/meldung/mehr-transparenz-zur-funktionsweise-von-google-youtube-instagram-co-erforderlich>).

e) Directing and influencing user behaviour: Autocomplete

The autocomplete feature on entering a search term might be very useful and can make the search quicker. However, it has also negative effects. It can reinforce stereotypes, because it proposes what a majority has searched in the past. Thus, it influences the search behaviour when distracting from the actually intended search term. Furthermore, it can defame peoples’ reputation when it associates a person with something negative, even if this just stems from previous searches and not from facts. Even more problematic is the fact that, similar to search result hacking, the autocomplete can also be hacked. For example, one company already offers such service for money (www.autosuggest-web.eu). A funny but also solution-oriented approach is the interview series where prominent persons react on autocomplete suggestions on themselves (<https://www.wired.com/video/series/google-autocomplete-interviews>).

f) Search engine results pages (SERPs) can put the content of a website into a different (and possibly wrong) context

A search for a controversial topic can list the websites of reputable organisations along with the websites with dubious information. For example, the search for “vaccination dangerous” results in a list of antivaxxer that also embed the website of the reputable German organisation Robert-Koch Institute (<https://www.rki.de>).

3.2 Workshop analysis

At the ELSA workshop in Graz (see Section 2.4) ethical aspects were discussed in group settings. This subsection summarises the discussions.

Page availability errors

A web page that appears in a search result could be removed after it was indexed. This leads to a 404 error. Though this is not a serious problem, it still constitutes a quality issue, and might decrease trust in the search result. A validation before displaying it as result could solve this issue.

Furthermore, it is possible that for some reason an existing web page is not in the index. The user can specifically search for it, but does not find it. This might also decrease trust in the search engine.

Related ethical values: trust.

Related stakeholders: content creators, end users.

Content quality

Content analysis is being done in the indexing processes. Different features of the web pages can be analysed, such as the overall content quality or if it contains different types of problematic content. This situation raises an ethical question regarding the accuracy of the interpretation and how it is perceived by the end user. Furthermore, the interpretation has also be seen in the light of what the content creator intended to express. Obviously, machine-made interpretations and quality checks are difficult to generate and have to be treated with care. If such an interpretation occurs in the result page, along with each result item, the user has to critically evaluate it. Though it might be a help for the user, it can also be misleading if the interpretation is made wrongly.

Different potential solutions to this ethical situation can be imagined. Offering maximum transparency about the interpretation process and its average accuracy would provide valuable information to the user. Conducting comprehensive benchmarking tests to assess accuracy can enhance the quality of interpretation, ensuring meaningful information for the user. Thus presenting diverse interpretations generated by various algorithms encourages users to engage in critical reflection upon their results.

Related ethical values: trust, access to information.

Related stakeholders: content creators, end users.

Problematic and illegal content

From a legal perspective, there is no universal regulation on what is illegal content, but there are different laws in different countries. For this reason, the ethical review of content is gaining even more importance. Unlike low-quality content, problematic content typically encompasses material that the majority of individuals would reject and find repulsive.

Possible solutions would involve automatic detection methods and manual systematic reviews, as well as take-down requests on demand. Automatic detection of problematic content could be feasible to some extent, but very likely automatic classification will not be always and fully correct. However, systematic manual review is expensive, and often performed by a work force that is not sufficiently paid. Individual feedback from people end-users underlies subjective assessments. So all of these methods have their problems, but in any case, some norms or explanations are needed to determine, what exactly is problematic content from an ethical point of view.

Related ethical values: trust, accountability.

Related stakeholders: content creators, developers, end users.

Personal and private Information

The processing (gathering, indexing, search and retrieval) of personal information creates ethical dilemmas. On one side, people (content creators) can publish personal or private content about themselves if they like. However, if individuals disclose personal or private information about others, the situation becomes critical. This leads to the right of being forgotten. People should have the right that information about themselves are removed from the index. In contrast to that there is also the right of the society to get information of public interest (e.g. information about a politician). Furthermore, there is also the idea of “freedom of speech”, that allows to publish at least personal opinions and relevant information.

A solution to these dilemmas seems to be difficult. It is unclear who should decide what information is allowed to be published and which information has to be removed. Even if there is a take-down process that removes information from the index, it is difficult to clarify all the concomitant aspects.

Related ethical values: accountability, access to information.

Related stakeholders: society, content creators, individual people of who information is published, and the project operators.

Reporting and blacklisting

The already described ethical aspects w.r.t. the web pages and content can be handled by reporting and blacklisting. A procedure, which is based on technical (button or web page for feedback) and manual (person who proves feedback) measures can be set up to remove content and/or web pages from the index, and blacklist websites to avoid future gathering. However, such procedure also raises several ethical questions (e.g., who decides what content should be removed or blacklisted considering the ethical dilemmas described above? How can a website be removed from the blacklist if it is not problematic?).

A solution oriented approach would involve a clear and transparent description of guidelines on procedures (how) and reasons (why) websites are blacklisted. Furthermore, a procedure should be set up that allows removal from the blacklist. The list of removed or blacklisted websites and their content should not be published.

Related ethical value: transparency, accountability, safety.

Related stakeholders: content creators, OWS operators, end-users, society.

Usage of the Index

Even if the index and content database do not contain problematic content, the data can still be used in an ethically problematic manner (e.g. racial profiling, spying on people for commercial use).

A solution to this problem is challenging. The most meaningful approach is to provide “Terms of usage” otherwise, End User License Agreement that regulates what is prohibited. A meaningful description of what is allowed and what is not in terms of use cases is preferable way out. A technical approach could be implemented by the need for approval to get access to the index. However, the question arises once more regarding who makes decisions in cases that are ambiguous and unclear. Related ethical values: accountability.

Related stakeholders: society, content creators, individual people of who information is published, 3rd party developers and users of index data.

Biased ranking

The ranking of the search result might be biased. During indexing, the page rank algorithm assigns scores to each page. Such static ranking method is not optimal for dynamically growing topics. Hence,

the results consider too much of the past and may not adequately address the requirements for obtaining appropriate results on growing topics.

A solution could be the HITS algorithm², which rather focuses on the topic of the search and is performed dynamically. The calculation requires more computational power. However, embedding it within a search application with only a smaller partition of the index, this might be doable.

Related ethical values: accuracy.

Related stakeholders: developers, end users.

3.3 Ethical values

This subsection lists the most relevant ethical values that have been identified so far (Table 2). This analysis is based on the project goals (Description of Action) and the discussions held in the various workshop activities (especially the fourth workshop in Berlin), as well as on literature review. Note that most values are closely interrelated.

These values listed below provide the basis for most ethics-related activities and documents in the project, such as the ethics assessment or the creation of codes of conduct which is provided to both external users of the index and application developers.

Ethical Value	Description and relation to OWS
Openness	<p>General description. Openness³ is a virtue of people or organisations that stimulates progress and growth, in contrast to closed-mindedness, narrowness, and rigidity. Openness can be practised in at least three directions. First, openness is directed toward people and is receptive to others, inclusive rather than exclusive, and welcomes diversity. It values (not just “tolerates”) others, and seeks to discover the gifts and talents of those others. The second direction is toward ideas (intellectual openness), which includes openness to creativity, innovation, and novelty. Third, openness is directed toward criticism. Besides criticism on technical or business grounds, ethical criticism asks if a technology or a business decision is good or bad for people or organisations.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. The openness concept in OWS context addresses receptiveness towards integration of new concepts and technical contributions, but also the usage and exploitation of the data and services provided by the OWI. It addresses a wide range of different types of stakeholders located globally. In addition, openness also includes the acceptance of ethical criticism of the developed software, concepts, and services. Hence, openness is also relevant to i) establishing OWI as critical infrastructure and, ii) building an ecosystem around it.</p>
Transparency	<p>General description. As an ethic that spans science, engineering, business,</p>

² Kleinberg, J. (1999). Authoritative sources in a hyperlinked environment. *Journal of the ACM*, 46 (5): 604–632. doi:10.1145/324133.324140

³ <https://ethix.org/1999/08/01/openness>

	<p>and the humanities, transparency⁴ is operating in such a way that it is easy for others to see what actions are performed. Transparency implies openness, communication, and accountability. Transparency also includes the concepts of explainability, observability, understandability, and controllability.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. Transparency in OWS context relates to the data and algorithms available in the OWI and related applications. Metadata, data analysis, algorithmic decisions, and the overall approach should be made transparent to the user in a way that the user can easily understand the matter, without creating a cognitive overload (e.g. caused by excessive technical data). Furthermore, users should have access to the data and algorithmic operations making them as accessible and understandable as possible for the user.</p>
Trustworthiness	<p>General description. Trustworthiness relates directly to ethics on two specific dimensions such as integrity and benevolence. A trustworthy party is one that will not unfairly exploit the vulnerabilities of the other party in the relationship. Trustworthiness correlates with trust, as a person can trust someone or something that is trustworthy.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. Trustworthiness⁵ addresses the processes of OWS that ensure integrity of the data and services. This includes a careful and reflective design of the processes and algorithms, as well as the responsiveness in case of problems. In particular, it needs to focus on the data and algorithms not only from a functional point of view, but also from the stakeholders perspective that make use of the system.</p>
Privacy	<p>General description. Privacy⁶ refers to the right of individuals to retain certain personal information without disclosure and to have protection against unauthorised access of any information about themselves that is collected with their consent.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. In the context of OWS this refers to i) the personal data that is collected by indexing and through end-user interactions, and ii) the responsible treatment of this data. Search engines need to respect the informational self-determination and privacy of every individual. Furthermore, individuals have a right to make informed choices about data collection, advertising, and personalisation tools. This also means that there must be easy ways to obtain consent and to remove content.</p>
Responsibility and Accountability	<p>General description. Responsibility⁷ refers to both the obligation and liability for which someone is held accountable. The obligation refers to someone or something that has to deal with certain issues because of a duty. The liability refers to the accountability of someone or something that has to give reason or handle consequences of actions.</p>

⁴ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transparency_\(behavior\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transparency_(behavior))

⁵ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43681-022-00200-5#auth-Karoline-Reinhardt-Aff1-Aff2>

⁶ <https://www.umsl.edu/~joshik/msis480/chapt17.htm>

⁷ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/accountability>

	<p>Relevance in OWS. Responsibility is an important value when it comes to problems with data and users, which require a careful reaction to detected and reported problems and errors.</p>
<p>Simplicity and Usability</p>	<p>General description. Simplicity relates to usability⁸ and means the usage of a system in an easy and understandable way, minimising unnecessarily high levels of complexity. Usability refers to the capacity of a system to provide a condition for users to perform tasks with safety, effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. Technical components accessed directly by users should be created in a way that they enable easy and understandable interaction minimising complexity and cognitive load. Dark patterns and functions with hidden purposes should be avoided.</p>
<p>Diversity (Cross-cultural sensitivity)</p>	<p>General description. Diversity⁹ stands for various differences as well as similarities between individuals. It is often mentioned in context of gender, ethnicity, age, religion, or disabilities, but in general diversity applies to the entire spectrum of differences. Diverse groups or minorities should be provided with equal opportunities, treated with fairness and respect, and not discriminated.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. Indexing and search processes should not only respect diverse users, but also actively consider the information collected and provided. For example, search results should contain unbiased information and indexed information should be tagged if problematic.</p>
<p>Sustainability</p>	<p>General description. Sustainability¹⁰ is a social goal for people to co-exist on Earth over a long time. Specific definitions of this term are disputed and have varied with literature, context, and time. Experts often describe sustainability as having three dimensions: environmental, economic, and social, where specific focus is on the environmental dimension.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. In OWS context all three dimensions of sustainability are relevant. The ecological sustainability refers to energy efficiency of the applied software and the hosting at data centres. The economical sustainability refers to the economical applications that rely on the OWI. Whereas social sustainability refers to the provision of a critical search infrastructure that has value for the society.</p>
<p>Reliability</p>	<p>General description. Reliability¹¹ refers to the consistency, dependability, and trustworthiness of a system, process, or measurement to perform its intended function or produce consistent results over time. It is a desirable characteristic in various domains, including engineering, manufacturing, software development, and data analysis.</p>

⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Usability>

⁹ https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/5620/Diversity_and_Ethical_Issues_in_the_Organizations.pdf

¹⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainability>

¹¹ <https://researchmethod.net/reliability/>

	<p>Relevance in OWS. In the context of OWS this means that the technology and its processes should be created in a reliable way, so that index uptakers can build on the technology and data. Data and information provided should be of high accuracy and quality in order to provide relevant search results to a broad range of active users such as uptakers and developers. This is very important for both establishing OWS as critical infrastructure, and build up an ecosystem of applications and data products. Reliability is linked to accuracy and trust.</p>
Safety and Security	<p>General description. Security¹² refers to protection from, or resilience against potential harm, hostile forces or unwanted coercion. At the core of information security is information assurance, the act of maintaining the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information, ensuring that information is not compromised in any way when critical issues arise.</p> <p>Relevance in OWS. The information retrieval, processing and storage procedures of OWS need to adhere to the basic principles of safety, data integrity, confidentiality and availability. This also involves measures for security ensuring the search infrastructure are resilient against manipulation and misuse.</p>

Table 2: Ethical values related to Open Web Search.

This list of values provides short explanations and justifications for why they are relevant to OWS. Given that ethics is an ongoing discussion, this list will be updated throughout the project. Future work might take into account ethical values from a broader set of 50 values¹³

Accessibility, Accountability, Adaptability, Affordability, Availability, Balanced Representation, Clarity, Collaboration, Community Involvement, Compassion, Confidentiality, Courage, Creativity, Diversity, Efficiency, Empathy, Environmental responsibility, Fairness, Flexibility, Freedom, Generosity, Gratitude, Honesty, Human Dignity, Humility, Human-centred design, Inclusivity, Innovation, Integrity, Intellectual property rights, Interoperability, Justice, Loyalty, Not Harming, Openness, Privacy, Quality, Reliability, Resilience, Respect, Responsibility, Safety, Security, Simplicity, Social responsibility, Sustainability, Transparency, Trustworthiness, Usability, User-Centred Design

3.4 Stakeholders

This section lists stakeholders that are concerned in some way with ethical issues and solutions (Table 3) of OpenWebSearch.eu project. This is not a complete list of project stakeholders, but highlights the ones on which the OWS technology has an ethical impact. A thorough understanding of these groups is imperative because the impact in terms of ethics varies across them. The individual groups are categorised into group types, which provides additional structure needed for the impact analysis.

The identification of the stakeholders is coordinated with Task 6.2 and is also reflected in the Deliverable *D6.4 Report on scientific cooperation, community building and stakeholder involvement*. The report

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Information_security

¹³ assembled by Nikolaus Dierks, <http://www.nicolas-dierks.de/>

provides a comprehensive description of the approach taken to involve the key stakeholders of OpenWebSearch.eu. This includes the stakeholders listed below, that are also described in Section 2.3 of deliverable D6.4. For them for whom specific engagement strategies are being and will be developed. In the current phase of the project, special attention is dedicated to policy makers (*political oversight and funding*) and the users of the index (*usage and utilisation*).

Stakeholders	Description
<p>Regular end-users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users of search applications • End-users of data products and related applications 	<p>This group targets the regular end-user that just consumes the various services with a respective user interface</p>
<p>Index users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developers of search applications • Developers of data products • Organisations or companies creating data products or search applications • Researchers and research institutions using the index for research • Educational sector (e.g. lecture on information search and retrieval) 	<p>This group consists of those who make use of the OWS index in any kind.</p>
<p>Technology and index developers, maintainers, and researchers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developers of the components needed for the index generation • Researchers on the technology needed for the index generation • Data centres where the index data is stored and the technology is applied • Data curators who take care for the data and content stored in the index 	<p>This user group consists of people who contribute to the creation and operation of the index</p>
<p>Contextual research and institutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal, ethical, and societal researcher • Business incubators • Policy makers • Educational institutions (e.g. schools) • Communication departments 	<p>This group includes researchers and institutions on cross-cutting topics</p>

Content providers and content creators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website owners • Website publishers • Media outlets 	This group includes humans and organisations who create and publish content on the web.
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Table 3: Stakeholders from an ethical perspective.

3.5 Outcomes

The ethical considerations on issues, requirements, stakeholders, technology, and solution oriented approaches made so far are intended to lead to several outcomes needed in the project. These outcomes will be part of and contribute to the ELSA Catalogue and Code of Conduct.

The first type of outcome addresses the development of the technology. Besides making developers aware of ethical considerations, a formal analysis of the ethical aspects related to Open Web Search will be provided. This analysis will lead to an **ethics-by-design or value-by-design approach** which provide guidance for inclusion of ethical aspects in the technology design, as well as an **ethical checklist** - for performing an ethical review.

The second type of outcome addresses the users and end-users of the technology and data. It will consist of **ethical guidelines and code of conducts**. A code of conduct or code of ethics sets out the guidelines and rules to follow, in order to comply with the ethical values and ethical principles. Hence, the code of conduct (or code of ethics) will be based on the ethical values identified in Section 3.3. A code of ethics is rather broad, giving people or users a general idea of what types of behaviour is acceptable and encouraged. A code of conduct is more focused and defines how people or users should act in specific situations. There are various types of users, which may necessitate different types of codes of conduct.

4. Legal Aspects

The overall strategy on elaborating and dealing with legal aspects consists in an iterative process of key activities, consisting of (a) elaboration and identification of legal issues (b) assessment of plans and designs, and (c) providing design guidelines and licenses. In the first research phase (year one) the main focus was put on the elaboration and identification of legal issues. These results are presented in the section. Based on these findings a legal assessment will be planned and conducted, and consequently design guidelines will be elaborated.

4.1 Legal issues

Throughout several rounds, the project members have been queried about their legal concerns and questions. This initial analysis resulted in a set of legal questions that have been categorised (see Table 4). The goal of asking these questions and identifying the issues was to set up a frame for further analysis of the legal issues. In particular, in the group discussion at the ELSA workshop in Graz, the following was addressed (see Table 4).

ID	Question or Issue
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L.01	<p>Definition of illegal content</p> <p>What makes a content illegal? Which types of illegal content exist? Which laws are relevant? Is adult content legally concerning?</p>
L.02	<p>Storage and Processing of problematic web content</p> <p>How should legal concerns be handled if illegal content is stored automatically? Under which conditions is the storing legally problematic?</p>
L.03	<p>Identified problematic web content and take-down request</p> <p>What procedure has to be performed, if problematic content has been reported and brought to attention? How fast has it to be removed? If we have a technical filter for illegal content, how accurate must that filter be?</p>
L.04	<p>Ownership of web content</p> <p>Are we allowed to present information of a web page as a result of a search request? Are we allowed to use web page information for further processing in applications? Which type or amount of information on a web page can we present on the result page? How should we handle web content that contains copyright and intellectual property content? Is it sufficient, if we respect the information in robots.txt?</p>
L.05	<p>Personal information and privacy in web content</p> <p>If a web document contains information about a person, can we use this information for further processing, such as displaying in the search result, sharing the index, etc.? What information constitutes personal information and potential privacy violation? Is it a problem, if the person himself/herself has shared this information and we respect robots.txt? Furthermore, is it a problem, if the person cannot be identified from the crawled data (because user details cannot be crawled)? What means are considered as being sufficient to handle privacy violations (e.g. take-down requests within a week)?</p>
L.06	<p>Handling a take-down request regarding privacy violation</p> <p>How do we have to identify a person who has the right for a take-down request? What legal authentication is required, considering that we do not have a user base and no users have accounts with our systems comparable to GMAIL? What is the procedure of a take-down request and in which time frame?</p>
L.07	<p>Qualifying web information and website details</p> <p>Can it be a problem, if a website or web information is automatically tagged with negative labels based on a content analysis? Can we be liable, if we give hints, which websites contain sensitive information (e.g. by providing indication which website contains GDPR statements)?</p>
L.08	<p>Sharing crawled data</p> <p>Are we allowed to share crawled data with third parties? Is it a difference, if we make the data accessible for single requests or if we share the whole dataset? Do we need to provide any further information about the shared data? Is there a difference between sharing raw data (crawled websites), enriched data (created from content analysis), and the index?</p>

L.09	<p>Take-down requests for third parties</p> <p>How do we ensure that (individual) take-down requests are propagated to third parties that have downloaded (part of) the Open Web Index and are using it to offer search services? Can we force them to delete these documents, or do we have to include something in e.g. our data usage policy?</p>
L.10	<p>End user license agreement</p> <p>How should an end user license for using the Open Web Index be designed, that especially considers liabilities that have to be passed on to thirds parties? Furthermore, the processing of take-down requests have to be included.</p>
L.11	<p>Current responsibility in data centres</p> <p>Who is responsible, if a software (e.g. crawler) runs in a data centre and performs illegal operations? The data centre operators, the people who installed/started the software, the developers of the software?</p>
L.12	<p>Governance and future legal responsibility</p> <p>Who will be responsible for the Open Web Search software in the future, if it runs in a data centre? How should take-down requests be handled? How should an end user license be designed?</p>

Table 4: Legal (L) questions and issues.

4.2 Legal Workshop analysis

This subsection provides a summary from the first workshop featured with experts in digital law. It outlines the general legal situation relevant to Open Web Search context.

Crawling, storing, processing Web data

Crawling, storing, processing, and keeping raw web content data is allowed, if it does not contain any illegal content, copyright data or personal information.

Illegal content is defined by national law and can be diverging in different countries, which makes it impossible to comply with all requirements globally. Search engines can be seen as intermediary service (Art. 4-6 Digital Services Act), which very likely removes liability of crawling, storing, and processing illegal content. Liability is based on either negligence (i.e. not following generally accepted rules) or intent (i.e. willing ignorance of risks – „don't care attitude“).

Crawling of copyrighted content is allowed under Art. 4 DSM Directive, however that exemption does not allow keeping and sharing of the raw data after processing. As an exception (Art. 3 DSM Directive) it might be allowed to keep and share copyrighted content during the research phase, in the EU, and for non-commercial purposes. Furthermore, the argument relies on “implied consent”, which means that anyone who puts content on the internet wants to be found (which is also the basis for commercial search engines). However, it is limited to the „necessary“ content (as little as possible) which might give rise to legal uncertainty.

With regards to data protection (privacy) law, „implied consent“ is not provided. Under the GDPR the only justification would be the „interest-balancing“-example on in Art. 6(1)(f) of GDPR (which was used to justify crawling, storing and making data available to the public in the ECJ decision¹⁴ on Google Spain regarding the right to be forgotten). While there is no case law on sharing index-data (as opposed to end-user-search), one might argue that a similar public interest exists (see the Digital Markets Act). Even a specific EU-exception would not ensure compliance in other countries (e.g. Japan) which also imposes limitation on re-use of personal data.

Taking action on problematic content

Search engine providers have to act in good faith, striving to do their best without being expected to actively seek out illegal content. Nevertheless, implementing filters to separate appropriate from inappropriate content is deemed essential from an ethical and societal standpoint. Furthermore, search engines are obliged to take swift action upon becoming aware of illegal content in order to address legal obligations. This is also true in research-only context.

In addition to automatic content filtering, manual take-down requests have to be handled. However, take-down requests necessitate verification to confirm the identity of the requester, ensuring that such requests are legitimate. In the context of a research project, the consensus is to delete any content, even remotely associated with illegality, to avoid any issues that could make take-down request operationally complicated. However, during the operational phase, arise additional challenges such as checking the ID of individuals filing complaints. This can yield to substantial manual costs. Although classifying of content could potentially trigger responsibilities (e.g., informing the police), it should be carried out from an ethical and legal perspective to maintain the integrity of the search engine and its adherence to relevant laws.

Sharing content and data

Sharing of raw data (WARC files) presents potential issues, as evidenced with the challenges faced by digital libraries. Simply collecting content from others and sharing it via one's own platform is not permissible, even if done for the greater good.

Under European law, raw data can only be retained until its intended purpose is fulfilled, after which it must be deleted. This implies that initiatives similar to Common Crawl or the Internet Archive would not be viable within the European legal framework.

The primary purpose of a search engine would be to serve search results, including the generation of snippets. This process necessitates access to large portions of content, such as the main text. However, the search engine would also enrich the data, adding value to the content. Sharing this enriched data might grant additional rights, such as ancillary copyright or database rights, but it is crucial to ensure that no problematic data is created through these enrichments.

Liability

Criminal liability applies to the human individual „acting“ or not preventing an act he must prevent under a legal obligation. This would usually be at least the person running a binary or including it in a Cron-job. However as stated above, criminal liability usually requires intent and rarely applies.

Civil liability for damages usually leads to internal indemnification („shared“ responsibility) – distribution of the losses. Yet, internally the „contribution“ to the event causing the loss is relevant. Thus, agreement to terms usually shifts risks among institutions.

¹⁴ EuGH, 13.05.2014 - C-131/12

Liability generally attaches to institutions, not individuals. Under most European jurisdiction, employees not acting wilfully or “grossly” negligent (ignoring indisputable rules evident to everyone – doing what even the “dumbest” person would avoid) will be indemnified by their employer (i.e. he will cover the damages).

Liability for copyright / privacy infringements for the index can be distributed by agreement. Since the relevant sums might be huge in the operational phase some kind of shielding mechanism is necessary. Under private law (without special legal provision) this might be provided by private insurance or creation of a limited liability entity (e.g. a non-profit organization, a LTD, etc.). However, both solutions are not optimal. Thus, specific legal provisions to protect the project would be preferable, however granting such privileges would be up to the European Union.

End User License Agreement (EULA)

Index data will be protected by copyright. At least there will be a protection by the “sui generis” right within the EU. Finally copyright applies to the software employed; index and software might be subject to different licenses.

EULAs for the current research phase should be drafted as soon as possible. They should limit sharing data to the EU and non-commercial research purposes.

In the later “operating-phase” Open-Data licenses might be used as a framework for later phases, but require adaptation. One should also consider multiple licenses for different addressees/purposes (multi-licensing like OpenOffice).

Governance

During the workshop, participants also discussed the potential governance structure for running an open web index. A governing body is essential for limiting legal risks, and it was suggested that a limited liability organization, such as a company or an association (in accordance with Belgian law), should be formed. It would be necessary to explore the available options and select the most suitable structure, while considering the risk of loss of control if powerful association members attempt to hijack the organization.

The governing body would be responsible for managing and running the services, as well as operational things like handling take-down requests. However, the infrastructure provider would not be concerned with these issues, maintaining a clear differentiation between those operating the services and those providing the infrastructure (zero knowledge infrastructure).

An EULA could be employed to limit usage and guide the community, serving as an important asset to demonstrate the intention of the governance structure. Participants debated whether a proper EULA or open source/open access licenses could contribute to demonstrating good faith. However, it was acknowledged that EULAs are likely more effective as statements of values rather than enforceable instruments.

Technically enforcing take-down requests on individuals who have downloaded data would be infeasible, but EULAs could mandate the use of the most recent data. Publishing a take-down list might not be possible, as it could infringe on privacy rights. The workshop's discussion highlights the complexity of devising a suitable governance structure for an open web index while maintaining compliance with legal and ethical standards.

4.3 Applicable Legislation and Jurisdiction

As the consortium comprises various organisations in multiple European countries, several legal sources that must be considered. Most importantly, that OWS.eu is operating under the scope EU's legislation and jurisdiction.

EU legislation

The relevant EU-Regulations, EU-Directives and EU-Decisions are to be used as legal sources as well as the general principles of the European Court of Justice (ECJ).

In the field of **Data Protection and Data Privacy** the **General Data Protection Regulation** (GDPR)¹⁵ needs to be mentioned, as the GDPR regulates the basic principles of storing and processing personal data. Furthermore, first assessment by the legal experts concluded that the project-related activities fall within the scope of the **e-Commerce Directive**¹⁶, to be supplemented by the **Digital Services Act**¹⁷ which came into force in 2022 and will be directly applicable in the Member States in February 2024.

The area of **intellectual property rights and copyright** primarily affects the exclusion of content from access by crawlers, in particular the `robots.txt` file. A distinction must be made here between research and commercial reasons. The EU's regulatory framework consist out of variety of directives and regulations. Crawling as such seems to fall into the scope of the **Digital Single Market directive**¹⁸.

National legislation

in addition to European Union regulations, the legal framework is determined by the individual national laws. Because of differences in the legal systems across countries , it is not possible to set out all relevant laws in this Deliverable. These national laws encompass the formal adoption of EU directives and other regulations within the fields mentioned above Each participating organization functions under its respective national legal framework. The University of Passau handles project coordination and operates under German legislation.

A prospective future legal entity will be bound by the national law of its registered headquarters.

4.4 Stakeholders

This subsection lists the stakeholders that are concerned with the legal implications of the project (see Table 5). Some stakeholders groups are responsible for ensuring compliance with the legal framework (such as project management, technical management), while others are affected by legal regulations (including data centres and content creators). Additionally, , policy makers play a crucial role in enhancing the the legal environment . A stakeholder analysis and elaboration is also provided in deliverable D6.4.

Stakeholder	Description
Project management	The project management has to take care that the technical products

¹⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679

¹⁶ Directive 2000/31/EC

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065

¹⁸ Directive (EU) 2019/790

	are compliant with the law.
Technical management	The technical management has to ensure that the legal constraints are taken up in the development.
Data centres	The data centres need to be sure that the technology and data available on their computers are legally compliant
Application creators	External creators of search applications or data products rely on legally sound index data. They have to accept the EULA and Codes of Conduct provided by the OWS.eu project.
Content providers	Content providers are affected because their content would be indexed in OWS, and could include copyrighted content or personal information.
Policy makers	Especially in the operational phase (after the research phase) following the research phase, a new legal situation becomes relevant that might require an update of the existing laws and regulations.

Table 5: Stakeholders from a legal perspective.

4.5 Outcomes

Beside the general description of the legal environment, additional specific guidelines and documents are needed for different purposes. These elements outline the building blocks for the future work on the Catalogue and Code of Conduct.

Guidelines for the Development. General legal guidelines have to be established that helps the development process to be compliant with existing law. Furthermore, these guidelines can also be used to do a legal compliance check.

Statement for data centres. A statement for the data centres is needed to explain the legal situation when operating OWS software and data, with specific focus on liability.

Requests for European Commission. Since there are severe open legal issues to be faced, especially after the research phase, legal safety should be provided by the European Commission. Hence, a request with an explanation of the legal situation should be made.

End-user license agreements. For users of the OWS software and data, a license agreement is needed that regulates the use, obligations, and liabilities. This is currently being created in T6.3.

5. Societal Aspects

This section gives an outline of further societal aspects that are not addressed by the ethical and legal sections. These aspects will be treated similar as the ethical and legal aspects according to the general methodology described in Section 2. A societal assessment will be conducted and suggestions will be given how to mitigate issues and strengthen the aspects described below.

Web search as European resource

Web search is a backbone of our digital economy and daily lives, but a few big tech gatekeepers control what we can - and cannot - find on the Web. This threatens neutral and transparent access to Web information and results in a huge economic imbalance as well as a lack of information sovereignty. Hence, the need for an Open Web Index as public good arises, in order to provide alternatives to existing private and commercial web search solutions. People, companies, and public institutions will be empowered to get free and unbiased access to web information, which decreases the dependency on non-European search engines.

Environmental aspects

An open and distributed index should be able to reduce redundant crawling activities at hosting providers and data centres. At the moment, each search engine that creates an index crawls each website individually. With a standardised interface according to previously standardised criteria, each hosting provider could crawl the data stored at their servers and make it available for others. This way, the web data hosted at one site would be crawled by only one player and not - by a multitude. This saves energy and would also lead to economic advantages for the hosting providers.

The energy consumption at the data centres depends on their geographic location and the technology they use. The geographic location impacts the energy production based on the local energy mix, including renewable, fossil, or nuclear energy sources. The technology relates to the efficiency of the energy consumption, including energy-efficient hardware or reuse of the consumed energy. The selection process of new data centres to be included in the Open Web Search project can consider an energy production and consumption statement as additional positive feature.

Economical aspects

A key goal of the Open Web Index is the development of an ecosystem of various applications that make use of the index. For example, search applications, large language models, and other applications and data products will be enabled through the Open Web Index. SMEs and startups, can make use of the Open Web Index and build their own search solution with commercial background. Considering the vast possibilities for potential applications and data products, new commercial routes will be made possible.

Democracy

Fostering and sustaining democracy calls for well informed citizens who also have access to unbiased and qualitative information. Furthermore, the citizens need to have digital competences regarding finding and evaluating information on the web. Thus the provision of unbiased information and transparency techniques to make users aware how information is searched and retrieved can contribute to improved democratic thinking of citizens.

Inclusiveness

Inclusiveness is an important value for a fair society that enables equal chance to all societal groups, such as all genders, ethnic minorities, or disabled persons. On a European level, also smaller countries or minorities with their not widely used languages need to be taken into account. Search technologies can address inclusiveness by enabling equal access to information to all these groups.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable outlines the considerations, activities, and created structures on ethical, legal, and societal aspects that have been completed or are in progress. Ethical issues, questions, and requirements have been identified and considerations have been made on how to translate ethics into

guidelines and code of conducts. The legal environment has been analysed and relevant legal issues have been identified. Finally, initial societal aspects have been identified and described.

Since this deliverable is the first one of a series of three, the work will continue until the project end. Focus of the next steps is on concrete elaboration of the topics described in the Sections 3.5 and 4.5 (namely, outcomes and products of the ethical and legal situation). The results will be reported in the next deliverable in M24.

Appendix

See included the list of Acronyms and Abbreviations used in OWS context.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Term
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
DSM	Digital Single Market
ECJ	European Court of Justice
ELSA	Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LTD	Limited (Liability Company)
MEP	Member of European Parliament
MP	Member of a Parliament
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprise(s)
WARC	Web Archive